

ISSUES OF IDEOLOGICAL SECURITY IN THE CONTEXT OF
GLOBALIZATION

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7663103>

ELSEVIER

Received: 19-02-2023
Accepted: 22-02-2023
Published: 22-02-2023

Mamatov Firdavs Alisherovich

The University of world economy and diplomacy in Tashkent
Student of the faculty of "International Law"
+998 (99) 101-40-64
mamatovfirdavs@mail.ru

Abstract: Based on a methodological approach, the article examines the concept, the essence of ideological security of society, as well as ideological security as a condition for the effective organization of the functioning of state power. The ideological threat is an immediate threat to the existing state system in the current political conditions of globalization.

Keywords: Politics, Globalization, society, ideology, Ideological security, Ideological threat, Socialist bloc.

About: FARS Publishers has been established with the aim of spreading quality scientific information to the research community throughout the universe. Open Access process eliminates the barriers associated with the older publication models, thus matching up with the rapidity of the twenty-first century.

The problems of studying and forming the concept of ideological security have always been relevant in political science. For many years in society, pro-Western and socialist ideologies have been criticized from both sides. After the collapse of the Socialist Bloc in Eastern Europe and the USSR, the problem of forming a national ideology that would determine and influence the existing internal and external political relations of young, newly formed states became urgent. Since it is this system that determines certain values, ideas, views, and the development of the state system.

"Today, the issue of the National ideology is very important in our country, which is moving towards building a new life and joining a number of developed states. "The Ideology of the New Uzbekistan we are creating will be kindness, humanity, humanism. When we talk about ideology, we mean, first of all, the education of reason, the education of national and universal values. They are based on millennial life ideas and values of our people," The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev said at the video conference on January 21, 2021.

Article 12 of the Constitution of The Republic of Uzbekistan state: In the Republic of Uzbekistan, public life develops on the basis of a variety of political institutions, ideologies and opinions. No ideology can be established as a state ideology."

As is known, ideology is considered as a complex spiritual and practical phenomenon, which includes a system of political, legal, moral, ethical, philosophical views and actions. Ideology, as a socio-historical education, is based

on the interests of people themselves grouped and generalized in a certain way by practical activity and need, united by institutional and group responsibilities.

The ideological structure of society has always existed, it has had various forms of expression from mythological to divine, from Utopian to Soviet. According to one of the prominent researchers of the problems of ideology, Professor Y.G. Volkov, the concept of "ideology" has been emerging only since the beginning of the XIX century and a scientific understanding of the history and theory of ideological teachings begins to take shape.

In modern conditions of globalization, it is necessary to clearly distinguish the "Ideological threat" from other types of threats, such as military, economic and political threats. Among them, it is the "Ideological threat" that has the greatest danger in that it is impossible to foresee what this threat will lead to and how to avoid it.

The First President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, I.A. Karimov, noting that one of the main threats to security is an ideological threat, wrote: "Today, ideological landfills have more power than nuclear landfills."

The ways of spreading the ideological threat in the era of mass globalization, the development of information technologies and the global network are becoming a universal threat to the entire civilizational world. Among such channels of influence on people's consciousness:

1. Information and communication technologies (e-mail, messengers, various computer programs, games, viruses).
2. Entertainment means that have a direct impact on the consciousness of people, especially young people (films, clips, music and content unacceptable in our culture).
3. Influence under the guise of "democracy", "Western culture" (violation of human rights, violation of women's freedoms, use of child, forced labor).

The priority direction of an ideological threat may be deliberate ideological influence and manipulation of public consciousness, the seizure and retention of power, the achievement of political, military and economic superiority of potential without taking into account the interests of economically full-fledged states, political and military power, which can pose a serious threat to interstate relations and the international community.

Under the spiritual threat, it is necessary, first of all, to keep in mind, ideological and informational aggression directed at any person regardless of language, religion, faith, against his freedom in the full sense of the word, with the aim of completely violating the spiritual world. Based on these beliefs, the formation of ideological immunity is the main task of any State to ensure security and stability.

Noting that "The Ideology of the New Uzbekistan we are creating will be kindness, humanity, humanism. When we talk about ideology, we mean, first of all, the education of reason, the education of national and universal values," the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan proposed to create an Institute of Socio-Spiritual Research, and the Republican Center for Spirituality and Enlightenment is now entrusted with coordinating the spiritual and educational activities of all state bodies.

It is impossible to imagine the implementation of this idea through the indifference of the staff and activists of the Center for Spirituality and Enlightenment. It is necessary, first of all, to realize that in the global world, the issues of "Ideological security" should be at the national level, be part of "National security". Bearing in mind that Uzbekistan is a multinational, multicultural country and that "Ideological security" should not be based on a mono-ethnic ideology, because this will lead to the division of society, our "National ideology" should be based on the principles of humanism, solidarity and patience.

LIST OF USED LITERATURE:

1. Авазов К. Внешние и внутренние угрозы современности, безопасность и стабильность в обществе и их взаимосвязь М., 2017 г., вып. 2, с. 103-128.
2. Волков Ю.Г. Идеология. СПб-Ростов/Дон 1996, Его же Идеология и гуманистическое будущее России СПб, - Ростов/Дон 1999; Его же. Манифест гуманизма (Идеология и гуманистическое будущее России). М., 2000.
3. Каримов И.А. Высокая духовность — непобедимая сила. — Т.: Узбекистан, 2008. —С. 113.
4. Конституция Республики Узбекистан. Статья 12. <https://constitution.uz/ru/clause/index>
5. Мирзиёев Ш.М., выступление на видеоселекторном совещании. 19.12.2021.
6. <https://www.gazeta.uz/ru/2021/01/19/ideology/>